

The Impact of Leadership Styles on Employee Performance in Public Universities in Kenya: A Case Study of Multimedia University of Kenya

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Abstract— This study explored the impact of leadership styles on employee performance at Multimedia University of Kenya (MMU) using William Ouchi's Theory Z. A descriptive survey design was used and primary data was collected from non-teaching and academic staff across various departments using questionnaires and interviews. Stratified sampling was used to select 194 respondents including 8 department heads who provided expert opinions. Findings showed that MMU's culture of innovation, quality and teamwork was found to be shaped by leadership which greatly influences employee attitudes and performance. Also streamlined work processes correlated positively with task completion, adherence to quality standards and job satisfaction. The study recommends investing in leadership development programmes to enhance communication, foster collaboration and align leadership philosophy with organisational culture to positively impact the organisational environment.

Index Terms— employee, employee performance, leadership, organizations, organizational culture, performance, public universities, teamwork.

1. Introduction

Leadership style and employee performance have been recognized as crucial elements in determining the success and efficiency of an organization. Effective leadership can significantly influence employee behavior, motivation, and productivity. Sundi (2013) proposed five primary criteria for measuring employee performance: work quantity, work quality, work independence, timeliness, and individual relationships. According to Gallup (2016), highly engaged employees produce high levels of customer care, retention, productivity, and generate higher profits (Luthans & Peterson, 2002). Employee independence refers to providing workers with autonomy and responsibility for decision-making about their tasks. An empowered employee tends to experience job satisfaction, contentment, and improved performance (Busara, 2016; Younies & Al-Tawil, 2021).

Successful organizations depend on high employee performance to meet objectives. High performance is achieved through job satisfaction and the right fit between employees and their jobs (Lado & Wilson, 1994; Dessler, 2011; Kristof-Brown

et al., 2005). The person-job fit determines employee commitment and productivity (Zheng et al., 2010; Rousseau & McLean Parks, 1992). Insan et al. (2013) noted that great employee performance is linked to high job satisfaction. Yahaya et al. (2012) emphasized the importance of providing a good environment for boosting employee performance and productivity.

Performance is evaluated against organizational standards (Kenney et al., 1992). Good performance indicates that employees meet assigned tasks and contribute to achieving organizational goals (Mwita, 2000; Cascio, 2006; Richardo, 2001). Performance in non-profit educational institutions can be assessed using criteria such as the number of employees and students, resolution of conflicts, financial sustainability, and innovation (Richard, 2009).

Founded in 1948 as Central Training School, Multimedia University of Kenya (MMU) has undergone several transitions, impacting its leadership, policies, and workforce. Currently, MMU operates under the motto "riding on technology, inspiring innovation" and the mission to provide quality training, nurture a culture of research, innovation, and extension to meet the aspirations of a dynamic society.

The study aimed to explore the impact of leadership styles on employee performance at MMU, considering the university's core values: professionalism, teamwork, adaptation, customer focus, integrity, equity, and scholarly values. Effective leadership at MMU is crucial in shaping the organizational environment, influencing employee attitudes, and ultimately impacting their performance.

A. Problem Statement

Kandula (2006) suggests that the effectiveness of leadership styles can differ considerably, leading to different outcomes in employee performance, even in similar industries and locations. The right leadership style can motivate average employees to deliver exceptional results, while an inappropriate approach can hinder even the most talented individuals from performing well. Ahmed (2012) supports this by stating that leadership styles directly influence how employees perform and manage their work. Effective leadership not only drives motivation but also

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aligns employee behaviors and attitudes with the organization's goals, ultimately enhancing overall performance. It is important for leaders to carefully choose and adapt their leadership styles to maximize employee potential and success.

Despite empirical research, there is limited evidence on the effect of leadership styles on performance (Mckinono *et al.*, 2003). This study aims to assess the impact of organizational culture on employee performance in Kenyan public universities, focusing on organizational values, leadership style, and work processes.

B. Research Objective

The objective of this study was to explore the impact of leadership styles on employee performance at Multimedia University of Kenya.

C. Research Question

What is the impact of leadership styles on employee performance at Multimedia University of Kenya?

2. Literature Review

A. Organizational Leadership

Organizational leadership is the process of influencing and guiding individuals within an organization to achieve common goals and objectives. It encompasses setting a vision, establishing strategic direction, fostering a positive organizational culture, and adapting to change to enhance the overall performance of the organization (Northouse, 2016; Yukl, 2013). Effective organizational leadership requires a combination of interpersonal skills, strategic thinking, and ethical decision-making to navigate complex organizational dynamics and drive sustainable success (Daft, 2014; Kotter, 2012).

Iqbal *et al.*, (2015) conducted a study on the of leadership style on employee performance and found out that the participative style of leadership has a greater positive effect on employee performance and in this situation, employee feel power and confidence in doing their job and in making different decisions. In autocratic style, leaders only have the authority to make decisions in which employees' feels inferior in doing jobs and decisions. In democratic style, employees have to some extent discretionary power to do work, thus, their performance is better than in autocratic style.

Obasan and Banjo (2014) while conducting a test on the impact of leadership styles on employee performance established that transformational leadership style had been proven to be the most effective style of leadership. The implication is that trans-formational leadership style will bring effective results in organizations because it motivates employees to go beyond ordinary expectations.

B. Leadership Styles

Wammy and Swammy (2014) define leadership as a social influence process in which the leader seeks the voluntary participation of subordinates in an effort to reach organizational goals. Therefore, a leader is a person who delegates or influences others to act to carry out specified objectives.

Memon (2014) describes leadership as the process by which an individual influences the thoughts, attitudes and behaviors of others by taking responsibility for setting direction for the organization. Leslie *et al* (2013) affirms that leadership is the ability to influence people to willingly follow one's guidance or adhere to one's decisions.

According to Sundi (2013) leadership is the ability to convince and mobilize others to work together as a team to achieve a certain goal. Leadership is the influencing process of leaders and followers to achieve organizational objectives through change (Lussier & Achua, 2009). Culture plays an important role in describing the leadership style adopted and distinguishes the members of one group from another. Culture and leadership style interrelate to each other. Dickson, *et al.* (2003) described the im-portance of culture and suggested that only the societal cultures point out the best leadership style. Every manager in management and operations uses a particular leadership style. The leadership style of these managers has a significant impact on staff morale and this, consequently, affects their performance (Shirzad *et al.*, 2011).

Bass (1985) demonstrates the relationship between leadership and culture by examining the impact of different styles of leadership on culture. He argues that transactional leaders tend to operate within the confines and limits of the existing culture, while transformational leaders frequently work towards changing the organizational culture in line with their vision. Similarly, Brown (1992) observes that good leaders need to develop the skills that enable them to alter aspects of their culture to improve their employee performance.

1) Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is a style that drives employees to achieve more than they had planned. This means that they go beyond expectations (Krishnan, 2005). Transformational leadership has a great influence on followers and changes their attitudes and beliefs for their interests. The behavioral change benefits the organization as well (Bums, 1978).

This form of leadership focuses on promoting development and strategic thinking in the organization and is more effective in the implementation of the change process than the other leadership styles. Studies on transaction leadership show that high productivity, a decrease in employee turnover and an increase job satisfaction are all due to this leadership style (Deluga, 1992; Marshall *et al.*, 1992; Masi & Cooke, 2000; Medley & Laroche, 1995; Sparks & Schenk, 2001).

Majority of the researchers had associated transformational leadership with employee performance and job satisfaction and argued that transformational leadership can be the best predictor of employee performance (Raja & Palanichamy, 2011). Transformational culture boosts both the organization's and the employee's performance (Bass & Avolio, 1993) without enforcing extra burden (Schlotz, 2009)

The transformational leadership condition is connected with high task performance, higher collective support acuity greater efficacy beliefs, lower harmful effect, and lower threat assessment compared to the transactional conditions. (Lyons & Schneider, 2009) and provide guidance to followers towards organizational objectives (Metcalf & Metcalf, 2005). Prior

research has demonstrated that followers who work under transformational leaders are motivated and committed which facilitates job satisfaction (Givens, 2008).

Transformational leadership style is entirely different from transactional leadership style. Transformational leaders try to develop the followers' full potential (Bass 1985; Johnson & Dipboye, 2008) by influencing and engaging them. Followers feel more transformed and developed thus organizational commitment is achieved by internal satisfaction and motivation as the employees find the organizational environment beneficial for their development.

2) *Transactional Leadership*

Transactional leadership maintain stability in the organization by recognizing followers' needs desires and then clarifying how those needs how and desires will be fulfilled in exchange for meeting specified objectives or performing certain duties. This satisfaction of needs improves employees' performance and morale (Daft, 2005). Transformational leadership is preferred due to its inventive as well as dynamic and accommodating nature (Bushra *et al.*, 2011). Employees can easily exchange knowledge among themselves and the leaders when organizations use transformational leadership style (Behery, 2008).

Transformational leaders are known to promote intellectual development, confidence, team spirit and enthusiasm among the followers, thereby encouraging followers to be more focused on collective well-being and achieving organizational goals (Aydin *et al.*, 2010). This style of leadership focuses on close monitoring, in detecting mistakes and errors and putting in place corrective actions to solve those (Obiwuru *et al.*, 2011). The transactional leadership strictly follows guidelines as laid in the rule book and prefers to remain in a stipulated framework for the optimal employees' performance (Shah & Kamal, 2015).

Transactional leadership has been in focus of researchers for many years and premeditated in numerous ways with different variables. Howell and Merenda (1999) conducted a research on the association between leader-member exchange, transactional and transformational leadership in forecasting employees' performance and concluded that transactional leadership style is a positive predictor of followers' performance. Bass *et al.* (2003) carried out a research for military platoon which was an organization, working in an unstable environment and it proved that transactional leadership increases performance among the soldiers. Transactional leaders communicate with their followers 'what they should do' and how they should do it' and then monitor them closely. Followers perform tasks and obtain contingent rewards upon satisfactory performance and get punished on non-satisfactory performance (Zhu *et al.*, 2012; Gilani *et al.*, 2014). Transactional leaders observe performance based on their predetermined parameters and take actions to change follower's behaviors so they perform as directed (Sosik & Jung, 2010).

Transactional leadership style is characterized by mutually beneficial exchanges between leader and employee to achieve the organizational objective (Northouse, 2015). In that sense, it is a soft contractual obligation between leaders and employees

(Jensen *et al.*, 2016; Ruggieri, 2009). When leaders offer rewards and observe performance for corrective actions this leads to a relationship between leader and follower for continuous learning and a better understanding of their role in the organization. Such employees feel more committed towards organizational goals (Zhu *et al.*, 2011).

3) *Laissez-Faire Leadership*

Robbins (2007) explained the laissez-faire style is a leadership style that abdicates responsibilities by avoiding decision-making. Similarly, Luthans (2005) defined laissez-faire style as abdication of responsibilities and decision making. Laissez-Faire is uninvolved in the work of the unit. According to Mondy and Premeaux (1995) laissez-faire leaders let group members make all decisions.

Though most leadership theories emphasize the importance of leadership activities including leadership reward/punishment and consideration, the involvement of the leader could have unintended adverse effects as employees' satisfied needs can prompt self-absorption (Koprowski, 1981). For example, according to Judge and Piccolo (2004) despite the strong positive association with employees' satisfaction supported by meta-analyses. There is also empirical evidence that extreme involvement of leadership behaviors has detrimental effects (Pierce & Aguinis, 2013).

Laissez-faire Leadership style is associated with role conflict, increased stress, and low job dissatisfaction (Piccolo *et al.*, 2010). Even though most empirical findings of laissez-faire leadership suggest its negative association with subordinates' attitudes and performance (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Judge & Piccolo, 2004), some empirical research suggests positive outcomes of laissez-faire leadership in subordinates' innovation propensity as it may facilitate an environment where innovation can occur (Ryan & Tipu, 2013). Therefore, the possible positive effects of laissez-faire leadership could also be explained in line with the notion of autonomy or autonomous motivation. Human beings have a basic psychological need for autonomy (cf. Liu *et al.*, 2011) and autonomy is found to be the motivational characteristic for performance (Humphrey *et al.*, 2007). Laissez-faire leadership could support subordinates' motivation to work autonomously (cf. Amundsen & Martinsen, 2014).

Laissez-faire leaders give their followers a full chance to use their capabilities to understand the ongoing problems by facilitating them with necessary resources and guidance and then offer them the liberty to make decisions accordingly (Chaudhry & Javed, 2012).

C. *Employee Performance*

Rath and Conchie (2009) stated that employee performance was linked to how well an employee achieved his or her goals and objectives. Employee Performance is the ability to achieve the set objectives within the required timelines and parameters (Yusuf *et al.*, 2014).

Atiku *et al.* (2017) considers a number of factors in measuring employee job performance. One of them is the level of productivity of an employee, which is measured by the extent to which the employee produces the desired quality and quantity of assignments. Another measure of employee

performance is the extent to which one demonstrates ability to clearly define solutions to problem areas. An employee's ability to complete projects within deadlines and other time-sensitive expectations is another measure of their performance. Employee performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him (Chhabra, 2020; Elangovan & Rajendran, 2020; Jnaneswar & Ranjit, 2020; Khaled et al., 2020; Russen et al., 2020; Sangeetha, 2020).

Having regards to employee performance Sundi (2013) proposed five primary criteria that could be used to measure performance, namely; work quantity, work quality, work independence, timeliness and individual relationships. Many researchers focused on the relationship linking job performance and satisfaction in the area of Organizational Psychology and found out that the employees' performance depended on employees' satisfaction (Yahaya et al., 2012). This indicated that great employee performance can be achieved by a high level of job satisfaction (Insan et al., 2013). Yahaya et al. (2012) concluded that for the employees to remain motivated as well as to boost their job satisfaction, employers should provide a good environment.

Paisey (1992) asserts that academic institutions that are normally seen to be successful are those whose management involve and emphasize consultation, teamwork and participation. According to Paisey, in a situation where some staff members do not agree with the policies and practices which have been accepted by a good percentage of their colleagues, they usually give their support. In other words, consultation, teamwork and participation are the common key characteristics of successful institutions.

Studies by Ryan and Deci (2000) and Thomas (2002) established that motivated employees are more self-driven as compared to less motivated employees which lead to availing developmental opportunities more correctly. Similarly, employee commitment is high when they are motivated as compared to less motivated employees (Guay et al., 2000; Vansteenkiste et al., 2007). Highly performing employees are able to assist organization to achieve its strategic aims thus sustaining the organization competitive advantage (Lado & Wilson, 1994; Dessler, 2011).

According to Wang (2007) managing individual performance in organizations has conventionally centered on assessing performance and enhancing incentives, where effective performance is seen as the result of the interaction between individual ability and motivation, this goes hand in hand with performance goals. It is worth noting that the higher employee morale and drive, the greater the chances that a company will not only keep the best employees but will also motivate talented employees to perform at optimal levels and reward in form of employee incentives has its magnitude of contribution to performance and productivity.

Employee performance affects the achievement of set company goals. Very low employee performance will cause the company to experience losses which can end with the closing of the company. The performance of every employee

contributing to the company is important. Therefore, every company needs to maintain and improve the performance of its employees in accordance with the desired goals (Hanım, 2016).

1) *Theoretical Literature Review*

The research was guided by William Ouchi's Theory Z, which assessed the impact of leadership styles on employee performance.

2) *William Ouchi's Theory Z*

William Ouchi's Theory Z posits that the survival and prosperity of organizations depend heavily on their ability to adapt to their surrounding cultures. Theory Z integrates individual achievement and advancement with a sense of community in the workplace, aiming to reduce negative influences and segmented decision-making by incorporating new cultural values.

Ouchi (1981) developed Theory Z after examining high-producing companies to identify common success factors. Theory Z extends Douglas McGregor's Theory X and Theory Y, focusing on the culture of the entire organization rather than individual supervisory styles. Key elements of Theory Z culture include long-term employment, consensual decision-making, individual responsibility, slow evaluation and promotion, informal control systems with explicit performance measures, moderately specialized career paths, and extensive commitment to all aspects of the employee's life, including family.

In the early 1980s, Ouchi applied Theory Z to schools, emphasizing trust, subtlety, intimacy, shared control, decision-making, training in planning, organizational processes, budgeting systems, interpersonal skills, long-term rewards, and the importance of high-quality education. Trust is essential and can only exist among people who understand each other's objectives, language, technology, and problems. School administrators must engage with students, teachers, parents, and the community to discuss school objectives and operations, fostering an environment of shared control and trust.

The features of Ouchi's Theory Z, including trust, shared control, decision-making, and long-term rewards, make it appropriate for this study. These features will aid in understanding the leadership styles, processes and practices that guide the existence, operations, and leadership styles employed by managers at Multimedia University of Kenya and their impact on employee performance.

3. Methodology

A. *Research Design*

The study used a descriptive mixed method design as recommended by Kothari (2004) for its comprehensive approach to data collection, analysis and reporting. This design was used to capture respondents' views and perceptions on the impact of organisational culture on employee performance at Multimedia University of Kenya (MMU).

B. *Study Site and Population*

The study was conducted at MMU, with a population of 378 employees comprising of administrative and academic staff.

C. Sampling Technique

Stratified random sampling was used to ensure accuracy and to avoid bias and the sample size was 194 respondents as determined by Slovin formula at 95% confidence level.

D. Data Collection Tools

Data collection involved surveys using self-administered questionnaires with both closed and open-ended questions and inter-interviews with key informants, that is, eight departmental heads. The research instruments were tested for reliability using test-retest technique to ensure consistency. Validity was established through content and face validity.

E. Data Analysis and Presentation

Data was edited, coded and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to measure central tendencies and re-relationships between variables. The results were presented in tables and figures and themes were drawn from interview data to answer the study objectives.

4. Research Findings, Analysis and Discussions

A. Response Rate

The study had a response rate of 77% where 150 questionnaires were filled and returned while 44 were not filled. The re-researcher also managed to reach 7 informants out of the targeted 8 for the interviews. This response rate was highly considered to be a representative sample of MMU employees as a response rate more than 70% is perceived to be excellent and satisfactory for analysis (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2008).

B. Demographic Information

The results of the study showed that participation from both genders was balanced, with 51.3% of respondents being males and 49.7% being female. 4 male and 3 female respondents were also interviewed.

C. Descriptive Statistics

Examining the highest academic qualification of the participants revealed a mix of academic qualifications with 32.9% of MMU employees having bachelor’s degree, 29.5% having master’s degree, 20.1% having a diploma certificate, and 12.8% having PhD. 5 informants were PhD holders while the other 2 hold Master’s Degree. On examining the year of experience of the participants, findings revealed a mix of both highly qualified and qualified individuals. 95% of MMU employees had worked in the institution for more than 5 years, therefore, had enough technical experience in the university

sector. Findings on the respondents’ terms of service revealed that that 92% of the respondents were on permanent and pensionable basis while 8% were employed on contract basis. This shows that majority of staff at MMU were employed on a permanent and pensionable basis, an indication that they had gathered high level of experience and their responses to this study’s research questions added value to this study.

1) Leadership styles

Transformational leadership as presented in Table 1 was the most popular among respondents, with 55% of the respondents supporting it. This was closely followed by laissez-faire leadership chosen by 30% of respondents. This style may have appealed to those who value autonomy and self-direction. The least popular style, preferred by 15% of respondents, was transactional leadership which is mostly based on a system of rewards and penalties, where leaders focus on routine tasks, performance, and short-term goals.

Table 1

Leadership styles popularity	
Leadership Style	Popularity (%)
Transformational Leadership	55%
Laissez-Faire Leadership	30%
Transactional Leadership	15%

Source: Researcher 2024

The findings presented in Table 2 offer valuable insights into the perceived impact of leadership styles on employee productivity within MMU. The data consistently highlights the importance of effective leadership styles in influencing employee performance and organizational dynamics.

The research findings showed a relatively low approval rating for the leadership styles employed by MMU's management. Only 4% of respondents strongly agreed while another 17.3% agreed that they approved of the leadership styles used, while a concerning 29.3% disagreed as another 26% strongly disagreed with this statement. This suggests that there may be areas for improvement in terms of the leadership approaches adopted by MMU's management.

Furthermore, the study revealed a diverse range of opinions regarding the impact of leadership styles on employee performance at MMU. With a notable 61.3% of respondents either strongly agree or agree that leadership styles affect employee performance, out of this percentage, 28% of the respondents strongly agreed while the remaining 33.3% agreed. A considerable 18.7% remained neutral on this statement, 12% disagreed and 18% strongly disagreed. This variation in perspectives underscores the complexity of the relationship

Table 2
Leadership styles impact on employee performance

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Std
I approve of the leadership (Transformational styles employed by the management at MMU	4%	17.3%	23.3%	29.3%	26%	3.560	1.18
The leadership styles employed impact on employee performance at MMU	28%	33.3%	18.7%	12%	8%	2.387	1.24
The leadership styles used in MMU enable the use of appropriate communication channels	6.7%	25.3%	27.3%	23.3%	16.7%	3.181	1.19
The leadership styles used in MMU enable sharing of information among employees.	7.3%	26.7%	30%	20%	16%	3.107	1.18

Source: Researcher 2024

Table 3
Correlation for the variable used in the study

		Organizational Culture	Organizational Values	Leadership Styles	Work Process	Communication
Leadership Styles	Pearson Correlation	.645	.603	1	.684	.777
	Covariance	.519	.423	.873	.550	.706
	Covariance	.565	.524	.706	.671	.946

Source: Researcher 2024

between leadership styles and employee productivity.

The findings also shed light on the perceived effectiveness of leadership styles in facilitating appropriate communication channels and information sharing among employees. In both cases, a significant portion of respondents 40% and 36.7%, respectively either disagree or strongly disagree that the current leadership styles enabled effective communication and information sharing. This highlights potential areas for improvement in terms of fostering open and efficient communication within the organization.

The data also revealed a notable percentage of respondents who remain neutral on these statements, ranging from 18.7% to 30%. This could suggest a lack of clarity or consensus among employees regarding the impact of leadership styles on various organizational aspects.

Overall, the descriptive statistics presented in Table 4.1 underscore the critical role that leadership styles play in shaping employee performance, communication, and organizational dynamics within MMU. The findings suggest that while some employees perceive the current leadership styles as effective, there is room for improvement in terms of gaining broader approval and fostering an environment that supports productivity, communication, and information sharing.

During the interview phase of the study, leadership styles within MMU were also explored, with transformational leadership being dominant in MMU with informant 7 positively acknowledging the emergence of new ideas from staff. However, informant 2 expressed uncertainty about the effectiveness of the laissez-faire leadership style, suggesting that its impact may vary across departments. This was also supported by Informant 4 who said:

“The effectiveness of laissez-faire management depends on various factors such as skill development, Empowerment and Ownership. This may not be suitable for all departments in MMU”

Feedback on leadership styles at MMU showcased a mix of perceptions. Informant 4 lauded transformational leadership for its role in motivating employees to generate new ideas whereas the laissez-faire style's effectiveness remains uncertain, suggesting a need for more clarity on its impact. These diverse leadership approaches may signify a dynamic organizational environment where different departments or teams may respond differently to leadership styles.

The examination of the general structure of MMU outlines a traditional hierarchical arrangement, with leaders in each department providing overall guidance. While this structure is described as harmonious by informant 1, it is not the case with informant 6 who deems the general work culture at MMU as poor. The existence of both positive and negative assessments suggests potential areas of improvement in fostering a more positive and collaborative organizational culture.

Leadership styles emerged as a significant predictor of organizational culture. The positive correlation indicates that effective leadership, characterized by qualities such as communication, trust-building, and collaboration, contributes significantly to shaping the organizational culture. This finding resonates with leadership theories that highlight the pivotal role of leaders in influencing organizational dynamics. Bass (1985) demonstrated the relationship between leadership and culture by examining the impact of different styles of leadership on culture. He argued that transactional leaders tend to operate within the confines and limits of the existing culture, while transformational leaders frequently work towards changing the organizational culture in line with their vision. Similarly, Brown (1992) observed that good leaders need to develop the skills that enable them to alter aspects of their culture in order to improve their employee performance. The low approval rate of the leadership styles used by managers at MMU coupled with the feeling that the current leadership styles do not enable effective communication and information sharing means that the university management needs to work on strategies to improve the relationship and communication between the managers and the employees.

D. Discussion and Synthesis

The correlation matrix table 3 reveals the strong relationships between key organizational elements, leadership Styles that in turn has a positive impact on employees' performance. The table above shows each variables' Pearson correlation coefficient, which is a statistical measure that quantifies the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables. Additionally, the covariance values are also presented, offering insights into the degree to which two of the variables in examination change together.

Leadership Styles exhibited positive correlations with Organizational Culture (0.645), Organizational Values (0.603), Work Processes (0.684), and Communication (0.777). This suggests that the leadership approach has a significant influence on the overall organizational environment, values, work processes, and communication dynamics that will result to either increasing employees' performance.

5. Conclusion

The findings reveal the crucial role of leadership in shaping the overall work environment, underscoring how clear leadership styles contribute to the development of employee performance.

The analysis reveals a significant positive correlation between leadership styles and employee performance at MMU. This suggests that the leadership approach adopted within the university, encompassing aspects such as communication, decision-making, and team collaboration, plays a crucial role in

defining the prevailing organizational culture. Leadership, characterized by clear communication, trust-building, and the encouragement of employee involvement, is identified as a catalyst for a positive organizational culture. Leaders who prioritize these qualities contribute to an environment where employees feel motivated, engaged, and aligned with the institution's values. This aligns with leadership theories emphasizing the role of transformative and participative leadership styles in creating a conducive work environment.

Given the significant impact of leadership styles on employee performance, the study recommends that the university should invest in leadership development programs. These programs can focus on enhancing communication skills, fostering collaboration, and instilling a leadership philosophy that aligns with the desired organizational culture. Leadership workshops and training sessions can be designed to empower leaders with the necessary skills to positively impact the organizational environment.

The study suggests future research on the impact of leadership succession on organizational culture and employee performance. Changes in leadership can significantly influence the cultural dynamics within an organization, and understanding these transitions can provide valuable insights.

Acknowledgment

I acknowledge my Supervisors Dr. Eunice Kijana and Dr. Kinya Kigatiira for their guidance and support from the conception to the completion of this research. My gratitude to all my lecturers, colleagues and management of the Multimedia University of Kenya for their support during my studies at the university. Special gratitude also goes to my wife Beatrice Ouko and daughter Emmile Ouko. I am also thankful to my classmates for their great support as we went through the coursework. I am also indebted to the respondents, mainly staff, from Multimedia University for their invaluable responses that enabled the completion of this work.

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